

present, identified insect damage, and documented beneficial insects.

Insects were collected from an advanced yield trial plot (1,080 m²) surrounded by other irrigated ricefields.

We collected 24 times (12 night and 12 day) from transplanting to crop maturity. Collections were from late Jul to early Nov in Ndop and late Sep to mid-

Dec in Mbo. A hurricane light trap centrally installed collected noctuids from nightfall to dawn (11h). Day collections were made at 11:00 a.m. with sweep net.

We collected over 40 insect species during the 2-yr survey. The table lists the 20 most prevalent species. □

Using chlorpyrifos to control gall midge (GM)

S. Srinivasan, M. R. K. Reddy, and P. R. Reddy, Agricultural Research Station, Nellore 524004, Andhra Pradesh, India

Efficacy of foliar spraying and seed soaking with 0.05% and 0.1% chlorpyrifos to control GM *Orseolia oryzae* in rice nurseries was evaluated during the 1988 wet season.

Seven treatments (see table) replicated four times were arranged in randomized complete block design. We sowed on 28 Aug in 1-× 1-m plots.

Tikkana (NLR27999) seed was soaked in chlorpyrifos solution for 12 h, then incubated for 36 h; sprouted seed was soaked for 3 h. Seed for the foliar spray treatment and control was soaked in water and incubated. Chlorpyrifos was sprayed 10 d after sowing (DAS).

We assessed percent GM incidence (exposed silver shoots and suppressed galls) by randomly pulling 200 seedlings per treatment at 10-d intervals from 25 DAS onwards.

Treatments showed significant differences at 25 and 35 DAS. Insecticidal efficacy was not significant at 45 DAS (see table). Chlorpyrifos treatments

GM incidence in the nursery with chlorpyrifos treatments.

Treatment	GM incidence ^a (%)		
	25 DAS	35 DAS	45 DAS
T1 Foliar spray of chlorpyrifos 0.05% at 10 DAS	10.5 (18.8)	17.7 (24.7)	37.8 (37.8)
T2 Foliar spray of chlorpyrifos 0.1% at 10 DAS	6.0 (14.1)	21.8 (27.2)	24.7 (29.6)
T3 Soaking of seeds in chlorpyrifos 0.05%	10.6 (18.9)	28.8 (32.4)	38.0 (37.9)
T4 Soaking of sprouted seeds in chlorpyrifos 0.05%	17.2 (24.3)	40.7 (39.4)	23.2 (28.7)
T5 Soaking of seeds in chlorpyrifos 0.1%	7.1 (15.4)	23.3 (28.2)	37.5 (37.6)
T6 Soaking of sprouted seeds in chlorpyrifos 0.1%	17.7 (24.7)	36.9 (37.4)	36.3 (36.5)
T7 Untreated check	24.2 (29.4)	41.6 (40.1)	33.5 (33.3)
LSD (P=0.05)	4.27	8.06	ns ^b
CV (%)	13.77	16.49	13.34

^aFigures in parentheses are angular transformed values.
^bNonsignificant by *F* test.

Relative prevalence of 20 insect species collected from irrigated plots in 2 rice-growing areas in Cameroon.

Common and scientific name	Relative prevalence ^a (%)		Remarks
	MBo	Ndop	
Stalk-eyed borer - Diopsidae: <i>Diopsis macrophthalma</i> (Dalman)	18.3	33.4	A major rice stem borer
Rice bug - Alydidae: <i>Leptocoris oratorius</i> (Fabricius)	10.1	1.8	Feed on ripening rice grain
Brown stink bug - Pentatomidae: <i>Euschistus servus</i> (Say)	8.9	1.3	Predaceous on several insects and also plant feeders
Cixiid planthoppers - Cixiidae: <i>Oecleus</i> sp.	8.7	39.2	Can spread virus
Long-horned grasshoppers - Tettigoniidae: <i>Conocephalus</i> sp.	8.2	5.4	Predators of rice bugs and stem borer eggs; also leaf feeders
Black lady beetles - Coccinellidae: <i>Hippodamia</i> sp.	6.6	0.1	Predators of many insects, esp. soft-bodied ones
Short-horned grasshoppers - Acrididae: <i>Atractomorpha</i> sp.	6.0	0.2	Plant feeders
Spine-tailed earwigs - Forficulidae: <i>Doru</i> sp.	4.0	0.2	Nocturnal plant feeders
Green stink bugs - Pentatomidae: <i>Nezara viridula</i> (Linn.)	3.5	-	Feed on rice grain during milky, soft dough, and hard dough stages
Cereal leaf beetle-Chrysomelidae: <i>Oulema</i> sp.	3.4	0.3	Foliage feeders
Shield-backed bugs - Scutelleridae: <i>Pharocosis annulus</i>	3.4	0.3	Known to be plant feeders, but feeding activities on the rice plants was not described.
Differential grasshoppers - Acrididae: <i>Melanoplus differentialis</i> (Thomas)	3.0	0.2	Very destructive foliage feeders
Seed bugs - Lygaeidae: <i>Eromocoris ferus</i> (Say)	2.7	1.4	Feed on seeds
Sugarcane borer - Pyralidae: <i>Diatraea saccharidis</i> (Fabricius)	0.2	-	Minor stem borer of rice in the area
Rove beetles - Staphylinidae: <i>Paederus grandis</i> (Aust.)	1.9	-	Known to be predaceous
Harlequin bugs - Pentatomidae: <i>Murgantia histrionica</i> (Hahn)	1.9	-	Found in ricefields, but feeding habit was not described.
African mole crickets - Gryllotalpidae: <i>Gryllotalpa africana</i> Palisot de Beauvois	1.4	-	Cut plants at base and feed on young roots, problem in unflooded fields
Red shouldered stink bugs - Pentatomidae: <i>Thyanta</i> sp.	1.1	0.4	Feed on plant, but not economically important
Ground beetles - Carabidae: <i>Colosoma scrutator</i> (Fabricius)	1.1	0.2	Known to be omnivorous, but activities in the ricefields were not observed.
Damsel bugs - Nabidae: <i>Nabis</i> sp.	0.0	0.1	Predaceous on several insect species

$$^a\text{Relative prevalence \%} = \frac{\text{Total no. of each species}}{\text{Total no. of all species}} \times 100$$

Total no. = Total count for the 12 day sweeps plus the 12 light trap collections per year.

Intensities reported are 1988 and 1989 averages.

did not adversely affect germination; nor were they phytotoxic.

Seed soaking and foliar spraying were superior to sprouted-seed soaking treatments in suppressing GM at 25 DAS. In some treatments, this trend persisted up to 35 DAS. □

Influence of some weather factors on rice stem borer (SB) infestation

S. Ramakrishnan and M. S. Venugopal, Horticultural Research Station, Tamil Nadu G.D. Naidu Agricultural University, Udhagamandalam 643001, Tamil Nadu, India

Deadheart/whitehead (DH/WH) incidence was recorded weekly during 1988-89 at the Rice Research Station, Tirur. Mean weather parameters 14 d before the observation date [maximum temperature (°C) (X_1), minimum temperature (°C) (X_2), relative morning humidity (%) (X_3), and rainfall (mm) (X_4)] were correlated with DHWH incidence.

The fitted multiple regressions to predict DH and WH damage were $Y = 1.2754 + 0.0913 X_1 - 0.04843 X_2 + 0.1067 X_3 + 0.2934 X_4$ and $Y = 13.9020 - 0.0336 X_1 - 0.0933 X_2 - 0.0980 X_3 - 0.0318 X_4$, respectively. The regression equations explained approximately 50% variation in DH/WH damage due to weather, but none of the factors significantly contributed to SB infestation. Instead, continuous cropping allows the pest to multiply. □

Chemical control of gall midge (GM) in the rice nursery

S. Srinivasan and M. R. K. Reddy, Agricultural Research Station (ARS), Nellore 524004, Andhra Pradesh, India

GM *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) damage causes seedlings to break while being pulled for transplanting. Populations also build up in the nursery to attack the transplanted crop.

We studied the effect of soaking seeds in seven insecticides (0.1%) and of two granular insecticides on GM incidence in the nursery during the 1987 wet season.

We soaked Tikkana (NLR27999) seed in insecticidal solutions for 12 h, then incubated it for 36 h. Water-soaked seed was used in granular treatments and as a control.

Nursery plots of 1 × 1 m were laid out in a randomized complete block design with 17 treatments, replicated three times.

Granular and foliar insecticides were applied (see table). We randomly pulled 200 seedlings per treatment at 25 and 40 DAS to assess GM incidence.

Differences in GM incidence at 25 and 40 DAS among treatments were significant. Incidence at 25 and 40 DAS was lowest in chlorpyrifos seed-soaking treatments. The other insecticides, used for soaking seed alone or in combination with foliar spraying at 25 DAS, did not protect rice from GM for 25 d.

We confirmed that chlorpyrifos seed soaking (0.1 %) combined with foliar spraying at 25 DAS controls GM for 40 d in the nursery. □

Incidence of GM in nursery at Agricultural Research Station, Nellore, India.

Treatment	Incidence ^a (%)	
	25 DAS	40 DAS
1 Soil application of phorate 10 G at 1.25 kg ai/ha, 10 DAS	24.1 (29.3)	19.3 (25.8)
2 Soil application of carbosulfuron 3G at 1.25 kg ai/ha, 10 DAS	43.6 (41.3)	61.2 (51.5)
3 Seed soaking in monocrotophos 36 WSC at 0.1%	52.0 (46.6)	64.2 (53.4)
4 T3 + foliar spray of monocrotophos at 0.05%, 25 DAS	48.5 (44.1)	64.6 (53.6)
5 Seed soaking in chlorpyrifos 20 EC at 0.1%	14.9 (22.6)	17.5 (24.0)
6 T5 + foliar spray of chlorpyrifos at 0.05%, 25 DAS	19.7 (24.8)	11.9 (20.0)
7 Seed soaking in phosphamidon 85 EC at 0.1%	53.2 (47.0)	55.9 (48.3)
8 T7 + foliar spray with phosphamidon at 0.05%, 25 DAS	46.0 (42.6)	68.2 (55.8)
9 Seed soaking in quinalphos 25 EC at 0.1%	27.9 (31.5)	33.5 (35.0)
10 T9 + foliar spray of quinalphos at 0.05%, 2.5 DAS	28.1 (32.1)	43.4 (41.2)
11 Seed soaking in methyl parathion 50 EC at 0.1%	59.4 (50.9)	63.7 (53.3)
12 T11 + foliar spray of methyl parathion at 0.05%, 25 DAS	42.3 (40.5)	54.0 (47.3)
13 Seed soaking in formothion 25 EC at 0.1%	48.8 (44.2)	55.1 (47.9)
14 T13 + foliar spray of formothion at 0.05%, 25 DAS	50.7 (45.4)	62.8 (52.8)
15 Seed soaking in demeton-S-methyl 25 EC at 0.1%	61.1 (51.5)	58.4 (49.8)
16 T15 + foliar spray of demeton-S-methyl at 0.05%, 25 DAS	60.7 (51.6)	65.7 (54.3)
17 Untreated control	55.5 (48.2)	61.2 (51.5)
LSD (P = 0.05)	12.30	10.28
CV (%)	18.09	13.71

^a Figures in parentheses are angular transformed values.

Mirid predation on brown planthopper (BPH) eggs

I. Manti, Sukarami Research Institute for Food Crops, P.O. Box 34, Padang, West Sumatra, Indonesia

We observed *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* predation on BPH eggs in an untreated IR1917-3-17 field during the 1987-88 dry season.

TN1 plants with BPH eggs were exposed in the field.

Field predation by *C. lividipennis* in untreated IR1917-3-17 at different cropping periods. IRRRI, 1987-88 dry season.

Days after transplanting	BPH eggs exposed ^a (no.)	Field predation by <i>Cyrtorhinus</i> (% ± SE)	<i>Cyrtorhinus</i> population per hill ^b (± SE)
35			0.25 ± 0.05
42			0.27 ± 0.04
49	329.9	3.85 ± 0.98	0.29 ± 0.05
56			0.42 ± 0.06
63	443.3	4.89 ± 0.77	0.63 ± 0.09
70			0.92 ± 0.11
77	562.3	8.06 ± 0.94	1.15 ± 0.12
84			0.82 ± 0.14
91	366.5	17.71 ± 2.57	1.25 ± 0.14
98			0.55 ± 0.08

^aAv of 30 replications. ^bCollected by FARMCOP machine. SE = standard error at 95% probability.